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FCGRT functions in senescence and transformation.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe a function for the FC receptor *FCGRT* in clearance of transforming, transformed, dead and dying cells at the plasma membrane through a mechanism involving recruitment of immune cells. The mechanism likely involved the function of CD302 and CD14 in the context of Igfbp5 signaling.

Citations

1. Low, B.E., Christianson, G.J., Lowell, E., Qin, W. and Wiles, M.V., 2020, January. Functional humanization of immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 1 Fc domain human FCGRT transgenic mice. In *MAbs* (Vol. 12, No. 1, p. 1829334). Taylor & Francis.